

A NOVEL W/TiN/Ta COMPOUND SHAPED CHARGE LINER

Zizhi Yan, Gaoyong Xu, and Jinping Suo *

State Key Laboratory of Material Processing and Die & Mould Technology, School of Materials Science and Engineering, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Wuhan 430074 China, jinping suo@hust.edu.cn

Abstract

The high density, high acoustic velocity, good thermal conductivity, and high dynamic fracture elongation rate make tungsten one of the most attractive candidate materials for shaped charge liner. But the disadvantage of tungsten is high brittleness. Since the jets of tungsten alloy liners will extremely quickly disperse after formation, the use of tungsten alloy liners has been greatly restricted at large standoff. In order to overcome the brittleness of tungsten, we use tantalum to toughen W, and use TiN coating to improve the interface. Then, W/TiN/Ta laminated composites with good toughness were prepared by SPS. Finally, the W/TiN/Ta laminated composites were processed into a shaped charge liner to verify whether it can form a metal jet.

The structure of W/TiN/Ta laminates compound

Structure of Shell nacre

Structure of W/TiN/Ta laminates compound

The influence of Ta/W thickness ratio

Fracture surfaces morphologies various Ta/W composites

Cracks distribution of composites with various thickness ratios

Stress-strain curves of Ta/W composites with different thickness ratios

Ta/W laminates composites with $t_{Ta/W} < 0.62$ exhibit macroscopic crack propagation, and Ta/W multilayers with $t_{Ta/W} > 0.62$ exhibit multiple cracks propagation. Formation of multiple cracks distributes damage and remarkably enhances the toughness.

Mechanical properties of W/TiN/Ta laminates

Stress-strain curves of three point bending of various W/Ta laminates

Tensile stress-strain curve of various W/Ta laminates

Explosion overload test

The result of explosion overload test

Metal jet formed a penetration hole on the steel target with a hole size of 10.3 mm × 6.5 mm and a depth of 28.5 mm.

The SEM image of the inner wall of penetrating hole and components distribution of Ta, W and Fe